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ONE IS NOT BORN BUT BECOMES A WORKER: SKILL RE-ARRANGEMENT AND WOMEN AS DESIRABLE WORKERS

In the 1990s' a body of literature emerged suggesting that managerial work is shifting towards valorizing feminized attitudes and behaviours, such as communication skills, shared responsibility, peer collaboration (e.g. Benschop & Doorewaard, 1998; Fondas, 1997; Rosener, 1990). This was an outcome of information technology diffusion, which increasingly brought to the surface workers' intellectual skills, and it made necessary to change managers' role, who could no longer exercise their power through informational asymmetries and hierarchical communication patterns (Zuboff, 1988). Accordingly, it was a matter of time until this feminized mode of working would become the norm, as team-based work was steadily adopted, including in assembly plants (Gottfried & Graham, 1993).

As a concept, the feminization of work has both a quantitative and a qualitative dimension (Morini, 2007); the former - i.e. the increased proportion of women in paid work - is predicated on the growth of the service sector and on the informalization of labor (Elgin & Elveren, 2021); the latter conveys discourses and practices that embrace qualities associated with the female workforce (Peterson, 1992).

This paper explores the hypothesis of the qualitative feminization of paid labor, whether the masculinized ideal worker is being displaced (Acker, 2007). It draws on 20 semistructured interviews with IT workers (n=10 women, n=10 men), based in Bucharest, Romania, which are representative in the context of occupations transitioning towards relying on intellectual skills. The paper will present four emerging key aspects of labor and how they relate to gender.

Keywords: feminization of work, de-gendering, cognitive capitalism

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PLATFORMS AND THE CRITIQUE OF POLITICAL ECONOMY

Platforms are now widely accepted as a term highlighting the role of data and digital technology usage in establishing interactions between multiple markets (Flew, 2021; Kenney, 2016; Nieborg & Poell, 2018; Poell et al., 2019; Rochet & Tirole, 2003). Data analysis allows for the streamlined and lean exchange of products – from personal data and lifeworld activities in the advertising business through labour, physical property, and retail. Economic activities in the platform economy can be best described as bringing the two-sided market business models, economies of scale, vertical integration, monopoly, and network effects to the core of digital capitalism. Compared to industrial capitalism, the novelty lies in at least three areas.

First, the output of expended means of production and labour power sometimes results in digital products and services offered at zero price. This raises the question of how profits are generated and how capital is accumulated. The second novelty is that digital product and service usage activity creates data inputs commodified as part of standard business practices for most platforms. User engagement and data analytics have become an essential competitive advantage. Third, in this brief but certainly not exhaustive list, the role of the state and law is essential in allowing capital reproduction. This is visible in intellectual property rights, taxation policies, and financial capital regulation. This paper addresses these novelties analytically and expands the debate about platforms beyond current Marxian and post-Marxian approaches (Jin, 2015; Srnicek, 2017, 2018). It asks what the critique of political economy and new interpretations of Marx (Bonefeld, 2014; Heinrich, 2012; Murray, 2018) can provide in that debate.

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Valeria Marina BORODI

Department of Sociology and Social Research, University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy, ORCID: 0000-0001-6380-8005

Diego GARUSI

Department of Communication, University of Wien, Austria, ORCID: 0000-0002-8101-0045

UNDERSTANDINGS OF JOURNALISM IN COUNTER EPISTEMIC COMMUNITIES: *THE CASE OF IL FORUM DEGLI INCEL*

Prompted by the multiplication of channels and the related authority crisis of several institutions, there has been growing interest in grasping people's understanding of journalism both within academia and newsrooms. Nevertheless, research on news audiences has traditionally tended to talk more about audiences than really addressing their perspective. One group that this research strand has largely ignored are those who challenge institutions' legitimacy in society. Meanwhile, structural changes in public communication have facilitated the rise of these "counter-epistemic communities", which challenge institutional forms of knowledge. Since acknowledging their perceptions helps diagnose their radicalization (Tomkinson et al. 2020), we considered it important to examine their understanding of social institutions, such as journalism.

Drawing on the concept of "folk theories of journalism" (Nielsen 2016), we focused on the Incel – a compound word of "involuntary celibate" – community, a set of actors, mobilized mainly online, who inspire and defend each other by creating a networked misogyny (Ging 2019). A content analysis of 319 threads concerning journalism published on one of the most popular Italian Incel forums has been performed.

Results are organized on three levels: descriptions of media representations; reasons for these representations; and normative understandings of journalism. First, Forum members denounce biased representation by mainstream journalists, that lead people to have an unfairly negative image of the Incel community. The reasons for this portrayal are attributed to the nastiness of journalists, their interest in personal gain – e.g., stirring up hatred to gain clicks –, and their ignorance of the Incel phenomenon. In line with the standard Incel rhetoric (Azzolari et al. 2021), the need for objective journalism that exposes feminist mystifications is strongly emphasised.

This study's contribution is twofold. First, it provides empirical evidence of how an anti-establishment fringe community, namely Incels, understands journalism, which is critical to journalistic theory and practice. Additionally, this understanding represents the first step in designing effective policy interventions.

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Giacomo BUONCOMPAGNI

Department of Political and social sciences, University of Florence, Italy, ORCID: 0000-0002-8251-1642

REPORTING ON DISCRIMINATION: COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND JOURNALISTIC ETHICS IN THE PLATFORM SOCIETY

Following recent global crises and with the emergence of collective traumas, new forms of anti-Semitism seem to be emerging within the public sphere, fuelled by symbolic violence, flows of (mis)information, conspiracy ideas. Anti-Jewish hostility appears to be increasingly widespread and reinforced, influenced by old images, fears and prejudices embedded in the collective mindset (Taguieff 2004; Neuman 2017; Neville-Shepard 2018; Weimann, Masri 2020).

Countering these cultural-communicative drifts is today a complex task for European institutions, including the mainstream media. Indeed, episodes related to anti-Semitism are becoming increasingly hybrid in their nature and therefore difficult to identify and report (JPost, 2021; Sorrentino 2008; Sorrentino, Splendore 2022). The presented contribution aims to discuss part of the results of research conducted within the framework of a European project investigating the level of knowledge/perception of anti-Semitic hatred among information professionals in Italy, where cases of hate crimes have increased since the beginning of the pandemic crisis (Wieviorka 2018; Monaci, 2022).

An initial background analysis in which news about the phenomenon of anti-Semitism reported in major Italian newspapers (from 2017 to 2021) was examined on a quantitative level was followed by seven focus group sessions (July-October 2022) aimed at Italian journalists. This second phase of the qualitative study was particularly interesting because while, on the one hand, the media tend to pay little attention to episodes of anti-Semitism (often reported as isolated cases), on the other hand, the lack of knowledge of the Jewish world in Italian journalistic culture seems to be the main cause of linguistic and interpretative errors, including of a historical and religious nature, as well as the circulation of toxic narratives that pollute political debate and human relations and risk overshadowing three fundamental dimensions of the journalistic 'field': culture, awareness and responsibility.

Keywords: journalism; media; hate speech; ethics; discrimination

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Alexandra CODĂU

Ovidius University of Constanța, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0002-6427-1075

THE LIMITS AND OPPORTUNITIES OF PRACTICING JOURNALISM IN THE DIGITAL SPACE: A GENDER PERSPECTIVE

This research aims to analyze the phenomenon of journalistic debut in the digital environment from a gender perspective to observe the limits and opportunities that female journalists face in their current professional environment. I will examine the case of a 19-year-old female journalism student facing a dual phenomenon at the beginning of her journalism career. Her debut article went viral on G4media.ro, a national media platform, accumulating over 100,000 views. However, the same article received over 1,000 comments on the publication's social media platform, with many of them being aggressive, sexist, or misogynistic.

According to the "Gender Barometer 2018" study, although conservative pressures are not as significant as in neighboring countries, "Romania mainly deals with anti-gender equality rhetoric and the demonetization of gender equality themes" (Grünberg 2019). Although it approaches a gender perspective, the present study follows the example of a debut in digital media because "mass media plays an important role in contemporary society, shaping public relations and private practices, maintaining and changing rules, representations, and ideological assumptions" (Roventța-Frumușani 2002).

In this context, the hypotheses I begin with are: 1. Power structures in society are mirrored in the media, specifically in the digital space, and are even perpetuated and augmented, and 2. A new generation of journalists is emerging in the digital environment, which creates the conditions for the development of new emancipatory practices.

Methodologically, I will employ a case study approach, as defined by Robert K. Yin as “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon (the case) in-depth and within its real context” (Yin 2014 cited in Hollweck 2016).

A preliminary result is that the debut in the profession becomes, in this case, a public event, in the sense that it is not a small, anonymous occurrence. At the same time, the significant exposure also brings many reactions that gather a range of responses related, on the one hand, to the debut in the profession, and on the other hand, to gender. We observe, preliminarily, that the majority of reactions are related to gender, not to the profession, not to journalistic content, indicating journalism as a space for challenging the legitimacy of female presence in the professional public sphere.

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Georgeta DRULĂ

Department of Journalism, Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies, University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0003-1628-109X

LEVERAGE THE AI TOOLS FOR CREATING THE NEWS WEBSITE CONTENT - ROMANIAN CASE STUDY

Introduction

It is a prediction that Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) will have a profound impact on newsrooms and jobs. So far, the demonstrated power of GenAI has developed topics of interest and also have approached critical perspectives about the involvement of machine learning and predictive modeling in content creation in journalism. It can be said that AI is rethinking what journalism is for. An AI expert Diakopoulos (2023) and his colleague Nishal emphasized that using tools like DALL-E or Midjourney, Bard or ChatGPT as AI models to generate synthetic visual content is still risky. These tools should be further explored to be productive in newsrooms for different tasks. The opportunities offered by AI technol-

ogies in journalism are currently grouped for several journalistic tasks: rewriting text, classifying documents, summarizing long documents, extracting data, and visualizing data. They believe that these tools should be used more as language machines than as “knowledge generators” in newsrooms. However, tasks such as sentiment analysis or fact-checking are important and are supported by these tools.

The purpose of the study

This purpose of this study is to explore the possibility of using AI tools in newsrooms. The use of these tools for various journalistic tasks should change the traditional editorial process, news production process, but they should also be used to define new strategies for audience engagement or content personalization. Data mining and extraction, data analysis, and data visualization can now be incorporated into in the journalistic process of making news. Data-driven storytelling is an undersized area that could benefit from a new approach using AI tools. This study will show the interest in the topic of AI in the news websites and also the opinion of journalists about the use of AI tools in their work and professional tasks.

Research questions

Several research question could be raised related to this topic:

Is AI a topic of interest in the news published on Romanian websites?

Who can benefit from AI in journalism?

What are the benefits of AI in journalism for content creation?

When is the best time to use AI in the journalistic process?

Why should journalists use AI in their work?

Methodology and approach

The methodology used is a case study as described by Priya (2021). The study has two parts, one quantitative and the other qualitative, based on interviews with journalists in the Romanian media landscape. The quantitative part collects data from Romanian news websites on this topic, to identify the interest of the Romanian media in this topic. AI tools will be used to automatically collect articles based on keywords used such as: AI, generative artificial intelligence, automatic content creation, ChatGPT, chatbots, virtual assistants. All these data will be processed using quantitative descriptive and correlational methods. The database is all Romanian news websites.

The unit of analysis in this case study are journalists for the qualitative part of the analysis. Interviews with journalists on this topic will be conducted in the second part of the research.

Possible results

The results will illustrate the recent approach in Romanian news website related to this topic. At this moment, we are collecting the data, so we do not have concrete results yet. The data from the interviews will complete this picture of AI in Romanian journalism, showing the opinion of journalists about this phenomenon and their profession. This is a work in progress, at this moment.

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Aurelian GIUGĂL

University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0003-3895-4697

Romina SURUGIU

University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0003-2731-2058

Anca ȘERBĂNUȚĂ

University of Bucharest, Romania

CLOTHING AS AN ELEMENT OF (REPRESENTING) CULTURAL BACKWARDNESS IN PSEUDO-RURAL WORLDS

Media messaging tends to confirm existing class stereotypes in our economic milieu characterized by ever-growing social polarization. Of all the visual cues that media outlets usually use to create class and habitus perception, clothing is some of the easiest to interpret by the audiences. Dress and clothes are closely related to the economic situation, social class, cultural orientation and identity (Worth, 1999). As other authors have pointed out, notably Uglow (1993), a wardrobe and meals can embody a whole way of life.

This paper explores the codification of dress in one of the most popular and long-lasting Romanian comedic TV shows, i.e. *Las Fierbinți* TV series, and critically analyses how it works as a symbol of cultural distinction (Bourdieu 1979). Characters in the show wear different clothes about a stereotypical contemporary post-rural social hierarchy. This hierarchy represents the peripheral cultural position of the Romanian countryside compared to the city and, on a more abstract level of representation, of Romania to Western European societies.

The paper argues that despite a sort of dress realism of the characters in the TV sitcom, the pseudo-rural cultural repertoire is framed as a failed attempt to keep up with the advanced urban milieu, whereas “traditional” dress for other characters’ acts as a sign of their inability to extract themselves from the post-communist rural habitus.

Keywords: clothing, *Las Fierbinți* sitcom, mediated communication, habitus, representation, Romania

DIGITALIZATION AND JOURNALISTIC REGIME IN TURKEY: ANALYZING JOURNALISTIC WORK IN DIGITAL AGE

The proliferation of digital media, the almost-constant change and update of popular platforms for news consumption and the competition for attracting more advertising revenue in the digital environment has led to a crisis-laden state for journalism, in which the traditional forms of journalism are rapidly losing their capacity to adapt to digital means of making and presenting the news. This paper proposes to employ the concept of journalistic regime as an analytical tool to analyse the digitalisation process in journalistic practice, with an aim of answering the question “How does the digitalisation of newswork in Turkey shape the economic, political and ideological dynamics of the journalistic regime?” The concept is defined through a labour sociological perspective based on the concept of factory regime articulated by Michael Burawoy (1985). Adapting Burawoy’s conceptualisation, a journalistic regime focuses on the “relations-in-production” within the newsmaking process and integrates the analysis of economic, political and ideological mechanisms at work process in news production.

Moreover, it focuses on the forms of competition, intervention and subsumption in the labour process of journalists in order to derive the character of journalistic regime in digital era. Following Burawoy’s extended case method (1998), the study has collected data from in-depth interviews with journalists working in digital native news outlets in Turkey and has situated the data in the context of economic and political developments in the media sector in Turkey. The preliminary results indicate that while journalists’ adoption of digital skills pave the ground for a more pluralized media environment, the digitalisation of journalists’ contact with their sources and with their institutions lead to more punitive forms of control in newswork, creating a ‘pluralist yet despotic’ journalistic regime in Turkey.

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Giedrė PLEPYTĖ-DAVIDAVIČIENĖ

Faculty of Communication, Vilnius University, Lithuania,
ORCID 0000-0003-0301-8903

Deimantas JASTRAMSKIS

Faculty of Communication, Vilnius University, Lithuania,
ORCID 0000-0001-8439-5297

Rūta KUPETYTĖ

Faculty of Communication, Vilnius University, Lithuania,
ORCID 0000-0003-2558-4906

PROFESSIONAL THREATS AND ITS CONSEQUENCES IN LITHUANIAN JOURNALISM

The purpose of the presentation is to demonstrate the professional threats (both online and offline) experienced by journalists working in Lithuania, which, according to the Reporters Without Borders (2023) assessment, operated in one of the world's most favourable environments for press freedom in 2022 (Lithuania ranked 7th in this indicator). The data of the presentation is based on a representative survey of Lithuanian journalists conducted from October 2022 to February 2023 (N=302).

The main assumption of the analysis is that both physical and psychological threats can negatively impact the quality of public information. It is noted that some social groups of journalists are more vulnerable than others (Waisbord, 2022). Research shows that women are more likely than men to be attacked online, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic (Posetti et al., 2020). Journalists from regional media, especially newspapers, because of declining circulation, digitalization, and declining advertising volumes, can face greater economic problems (Nielsen, 2015) as well as having potentially greater influence from local authorities, politicians, local advertisers, or information sources (Lankauskas, 2018). The potential threat to a journalist from different sources can lead to self-censorship and avoiding critical reporting of government actions (Hasan, Wadud, 2020). It can also affect the journalist's well-being as well as their attitude towards journalism. Thus, the relationships between experienced threats of journalists and self-censorship, journalists' well-being, and their attitude towards journalism will be shown during the presentation.

The data indicates that most often journalists in Lithuania experience psychological threats, particularly demeaning or hateful speech, public discrediting of journalist job, and questioning of personal morality. Less often are experienced physical, legal, or cyber threats. Male journalists are more likely than female journalists to be threatened in some way. regional journalists are the most vulnerable

and reported experiencing more different types of threats than journalists from national commercial or public media. The analysis of data reveal that there is statistically significant correlation between the experienced threats and emotional well-being of journalists. Journalists who are more exposed to threats are more likely to feel stressed at work and are more likely to use self-censorship to protect themselves.

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Keywords: journalists, media, professional threats, safety, self-censorship

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Mădălina MORARU

University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0001-5976-7968

ADVERTISING AS A MEANS OF REVEALING CONSUMERS' VULNERABILITY AND BEHAVIOUR CHANGES

The main purpose of this study consists in approaching advertising as a core source of changing young consumers' behaviour. However, global brands such as KFC, Coca-Cola, Vodafone have been trying to approach their communication from a critical perspective, knowing that digital technology might negatively influence their values and relationship with consumers.

According to Eurostat, in 2023 the Internet use by individuals aged 16 to 74 reaches in Romania 89%. With a potential ad reach of 67.3% of the entire population, YouTube continues to be the preferred platform for watching online videos in Romania (<https://mediafactbook.ro/MFB2023.pdf>, pp.61-62). Updates from Google's advertising resources indicate that YouTube has 13.5M users in Romania. In this growing digital context, advertising takes advantages of influencing consumers' behaviour, sometimes even positively. This research focuses on analysing few series of KFC campaigns running on YouTube in Romania (<https://www.youtube.com/@kfcro>): **Social me, When your mother leaves you, RANDOM, Friendzone and The Croppers.**

The main research questions are: **What are the main social values endangered by KFC YouTube commercials? Which are the negative consequences upon youth generated by digital KFC campaigns? Which brand values have been promoted on YouTube in the previous series? What are the solutions of crisis communication offered by the brand? How much are KFC campaigns influenced by gender and relationship between generations?**

As a qualitative research method, a multimodal discourse analysis was conducted to investigate KFC YouTube commercials on extralinguistic (visual) and linguistic level. Regarding potential results, this study delivers the influences of KFC campaigns towards consumers' behaviour such as: social media addiction, communication barriers, gender inequality and a distance from authenticity in the Romanian society.

Keywords: digital advertising, consumers' behaviour, YouTube, crisis

Chiara PERIN

PhD Candidate in “Sociology and Methodology of Social Research” at the NASP Graduate School (University of Milan) with a scholarship awarded from the University of Turin, Italy, ORCID: 0000-0001-8788-0116

GENDER WARS: REDDIT STRIKES BACK. EXPLORING THE CONSTRUCTION OF GENDER AND SEXUALITY WITHIN THE ONLINE MASTURBATION AND PORNOGRAPHY ABSTINENCE SUBREDDIT R/NOFAP

The present research explores how the growing practice of abstention from masturbation and pornography, known as NoFap, is constructed and negotiated in homosocial Reddit subcultures and what are the meanings attached to it in relation to gender and sexuality. NoFap broadly refers to the digital spaces advocating abstinence from pornography and masturbation as a strategy to overcome self-disgnosed porn addiction, porn overuse and compulsive sexual behaviours. The headquarters of NoFap is the r/NoFap channel on Reddit, in which the number of members doubled from 477k in 2020 (Hartmann, 2020) to 1.1m in 2022 (r/NoFap, Dec 2022).

The related conversations are dominated by “strongly heterosexual male tenor” tropes (Taylor and Jackson, 2018: 624) such as evolutionary narratives on gender and masculinity where men's sexual entitlement to women is an asset (Burnett, 2021; Meenagh, 2020) and the heteronormative coital an imperative (McPhillips et al., 2001). Studying the meanings attached to the NoFap practice and the related subreddit reveals how powerful technologies are in the relentless process of construction of our identity and sexuality.

Accordingly, this presentation centers on the ways in which the sociotechnical infrastructures and affordances of the Reddit platform, influenced by geek subcultures and STEM interests, contribute to producing normative identities and spreading toxic technocultures rooted in retrograde ideas of gender, sexual identity, sexuality and race (Massanari, 2015). Of particular interest is the utilization of the Reddit platform by NoFap members as a tool for monitoring, disciplining, and controlling their masculinity and sexuality. The platform and its affordances are integral components of their recovery process, functioning as a mechanism for constructing normative gender identity and sexuality through regulation and discipline.

This research adopts a digital ethnography approach within the r/NoFap community, incorporating computational tools as an integral part of the ethnographic continuum. The intention is to avoid extractive logic and metric-based debates on societal issues, maintaining a qualitative perspective while creatively integrating computational and qualitative methods through an inductive approach (Brown, 2019). This approach involves engaging with both the language of the community and the language of the machines that structure the online community. Embarking on an ethnography within digital spaces can be a complex endeavour, as noted by Abidin and De Seta (2020), given the intricate ecology influenced by models, algorithms, and metadata (Hine, 2020). This complexity is further compounded by the sensitivity and potential toxicity within the NoFap context, necessitating specific methodological and positionality choices that a feminist reflexive standpoint helped me to navigate and mitigate (Hall and Davis, 2021; Jordan, 2018; Dorion, 2021).

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Raluca PETRE

Ovidius University of Constanța, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0001-5976-7968

DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE OVER THE PLATFORM; THE CASE OF THE EUROPEAN BROADCASTING UNION

Social and digital inequalities are realities that we are increasingly facing. At the same time, they are not a datum, but capital driven institutional structurations that have as effect a differentiated access and space of usage of media resources. It is in this vain that in this paper I discuss democratic governance as a mean to better shape our media landscape. I believe it is possible to merge the most up to date business model, the platform, with democratic governance practices in order to improve the access and fair usage of quality content for all.

In order to substantiate this claim I perform an institutional analysis of the European Broadcasting Union governance practices. EBU is the association of public service media providers from Europe, and beyond. Together, the Members of EBU reach more than one billion people in Europe and around the world, making it the most relevant media association of the world, and a potential role mode in the media sector. It is an institutional structuration that already functions as a platform (Petre, 2023), but that has as core governance practices the principle of fair representation of all its constituents, as well as democratic procedures for voting and general decision making. The institutional analysis that I undertake aims to show a way out of the opaque, algorithm driven governance practices that are currently the main way to operate in the world of high-tech technological giants.

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Nadine SHANAHAN

The University of Liverpool, UK, ORCID: 0009-0007-0203-7981

IDEAL WOMANHOOD: A DIGITAL ETHNOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF THE CONSTRUCTION, NEGOTIATION AND PERFORMATIVITY OF FEMININITY ON INSTAGRAM

This paper investigates how women navigate ideal womanhood and how they utilise Instagram as a tool to construct their femininity. Instagram has the ability to construct a dominant version of ideal womanhood through its constant flow of visual content. Social benchmarks relating to beauty, the body, careers, and home life persistently inundate the female digital sphere.

Postfeminists refer to the gendered expectation to meet these standards as 'having it all' (McRobbie 2015; Gill, 2007). There is a heightened visibility for women on Instagram, creating intense pressure to meet the ideals of femininity. Here, I investigate how these concepts are underpinned by philosophical ideas such as postfeminism and neoliberalism, as they produce a culture of self-surveillance, discipline, and the prioritisation of successful womanhood (Clack and Paule, 2019). I am also interested in how women reject the ideal standards of femininity and how they utilise Instagram as a means to do so. Additionally, I seek to discover how ethnicity, class and sexuality impact women's relationship with ideal womanhood.

My methodology adopts a digital ethnography of Instagram, examining 13 months of Instagram data. This is combined with semi-structured interviews with 13 women. Several methodological choices have provided the participants with a greater sense of agency in the research process. My study also has an auto-ethnographic element, as my own Instagram data falls within the collection. These steps have fostered a collaborative research environment where women can share experiences. This will be a powerful aspect of the research that will enrich the study and create a sense of solidarity amongst women navigating ideal womanhood.

My initial findings illustrate a resistance to ideal womanhood and an active choice to construct an individualised version of the ideal through personal Instagram feeds. Many of the women highlight a conscious decision in curating a feed that reflects a femininity closer to their own rather than the ideal. Additionally, many of the women reject the postfeminist-neoliberal notion of competition between women through the way they use Instagram. My work challenges Ideal womanhood and highlights women's agency in the construction of femininity.

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Romina SURUGIU

University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0003-2731-2058

Adriana ȘTEFĂNEL

University of Bucharest, Romania, ORCID: 0000-0003-3050-0631

CITIZENS' RESPONSE TO A POPULIST DISCOURSE. EVIDENCE FROM THE CRISIS OF ROMANIA'S SCHENGEN ACCESSION

After Brexit and Trump's victory in the USA, there has been a wave of research on the disruptive effects of social media on politics, however, there is little focus on people's voice. There are several influential articles that analyze attitudes that are associated with voting for populist parties, the practices used by populist politicians to trigger users' behavior on social media, and gain exposure to populist discourse, but just a few that analyze the contribution of ordinary citizens on social media. Considering the limited body of research in this field, this article answers the following questions:

Q1. How ordinary citizens respond to populist messages distributed through social media platforms?

Q2. To what extent does their response contain populist elements?

The aim of the paper is to fill the gap in the existing body of research on populism, as it is predominantly concentrates on political figures rather than the ordinary people. This study seeks to bridge this gap by evaluating the prevalence of populism and examining the populist discourse among citizens in online comments. Methodologically, this research employs quantitative and qualitative content analysis.

To effectively address the aforementioned questions, we will select a subject with inherent populist attributes and a populist political party that has an active presence on Facebook and other social media.

There is a consensus in the literature that populism thrives during times of perceived/self-inflicted crises, since populist attitudes are consistently associated with anxiety about the future of one's group or country, with anger, protest, insecurity, and an overall pessimism about the state of society. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, we will select the case of the delay of Romania and Bulgaria's accession to the Schengen Area in 2022. While this event may not constitute a significant crisis, it displays populist potential, as it may be interpreted as an example of the Romanian political class inability to accomplish the main objectives of the country it represents.

Panayiota TSATSOU

Sir Lenny Henry Centre for Media Diversity, College of Media & English, Birmingham City University (BCU), ORCID: 0000-0001-6670-4711

A DECOLONIAL PERSPECTIVE ON RESEARCHING VULNERABLE PEOPLE'S DIGITAL INCLUSION: THE SOCIAL LAB PROPOSAL

Adopting a social decolonial perspective on exploring vulnerable people's digital inclusion, this paper proposes a social lab that *mélanges* theory and real-life experiences and puts together collaborative practices between stakeholders and vulnerable people, thus a) operationalising a theoretical construct that combines two controversial and seemingly unrelated theoretical approaches - intersection-

ality theory (Crenshaw, 1989) and Foucault's social theory (1975, 2008) and b) developing a transdisciplinary account of the real life experiences of different groups of vulnerable people and the related barriers to, benefits of, as well as tensions and complex dynamics in their relationships with digital technologies.

Epistemologically, this paper departs from materialistic and education-oriented approaches to digital inclusion and expands on discipline-specific insights into vulnerable groups, aiming at transdisciplinary knowledge. **Theoretically**, this paper brings together theories that can inform the core of decolonization practices, thus placing the emphasis back on deeper power, hierarchical and social colonizing forces that lead to digital and social marginalization. **Empirically**, the proposed social lab employs a methodology where stakeholder and vulnerable members will work together through mutual-learning and a three-staged progress work that involves a series of qualitative and quantitative methods and thus both bottom-up and top-down data collection and knowledge generation. **Policy-wise**, the paper's proposal stresses the importance of obtaining decolonizing transdisciplinary knowledge on patterns in vulnerable people's digital inclusion for the purpose of designing new policies and related action.

Keywords: decolonialism, digital inclusion, Foucault, intersectionality, social lab, social theory, vulnerability

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Cora VAN LEEUWEN

Ibec-SMIT- Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium, ORCID: 0000-0002-3536-5881

An JACOBS

Ibec-SMIT- Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium, ORCID: 0000-0001-8058-1455

Leona CRAFFERT

University of the Western Cape, South Africa

TAKE A DATA WALK WITH ME! INTRODUCING A METHOD TO CREATE AWARENESS OF DATAFICATION IN OLDER ADULTS

The results of Artificial Intelligence and algorithms rely on the quality of data collected (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020; O'Neil, 2017). Studies have shown that this quality

is unreliable when it comes to older adults due to both a lack in representation in the data (Chu et al., 2022; Fernández-Ardèvol & Grenier, 2022; Rosales et al., 2023; Rosales & Fernández-Ardèvol, 2020; Sourbati & Behrendt, 2020) and in the design teams making decisions during the creation (Rosales & Svensson, 2021; Stypińska et al., 2023; Svensson, 2023). This is also a form of what has been called Digital Ageism (Chu et al., 2022; Rosales et al., 2023).

However, in order to address digital ageism and its effects it is necessary to create awareness of the lack of data collection and processing (Fernández-Ardèvol & Grenier, 2022). Achieving this is hard for a concept that is difficult to envision within your daily activities (Gran et al., 2021; Hargittai et al., 2020). To counter this we adjusted and applied the data walk method to older adults (Breuer et al., 2023; Powell, 2018). This research aims to answer the following question: how do older adults experience the smart city's data practices when they are made aware of it?

We will first discuss the adjustments of the data walk and then present as a use case the results of a series of data walks organized in Flanders. The use case will discuss how the older adult perceives artificial intelligence, their role in data collection, the experience of the walk shop, and finally if they intent to change their behavior towards data collection and data processing. The results show that by providing older adults a means to connect with a relatively obscure and incomprehensible technology it is possible to have discussions about implications of those gaps in data collection and processing concerning their age category. The awareness ensures that they can make an informed choice of participating in data collection activities.

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Andrea VOLTERRANI

University of Rome Tor Vergata, Italy, ORCID: 0000-0003-2453-0025

VULNERABILITY AND LIMINAL COMMUNITIES. WHAT ROLES FOR HYBRID PARTICIPATION PROCESSES

If we consider the digital inclusion model, urban liminal communities become a fascinating phenomenon. These communities are localised groups that exist on the margins of society, in a state of intermediation. Liminal communities are characterised by spatial, economic, social and cultural marginality, resulting in limited access to basic services and opportunities. However, they may also show a significant interest in the digital dimension as a means to gain opportunities for public self-representation, create hybrid (digital-physical) cohesive groups and enable new connective and collective actions to overcome vulnerabilities. In this perspective, through hybrid participatory processes, it facilitates self-reflection and discussion of relevant community issues, generating innovative pathways for social development and inclusion.

This dual model of physical and digital living can help liminal communities overcome spatial and digital vulnerability, creating opportunities for community building through bottom-up initiatives. At the same time, it is crucial to carefully consider the dangers associated with the deep mediatization model, which can lead to further forms of digital exclusion. To prevent this from happening, we need to ensure that digital access technologies are truly inclusive and shared through authentic participation processes in the context of liminal communities. Our paper draws on empirical material from field research in 14 urban communities in Southern Italy to demonstrate how liminal communities act and communicate as a complex and multifaceted subject.

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Tsatsou P., 2022, eds, *Vulnerable People and Digital Inclusion*, Palgrave MacMillan, Cham.

LOCAL NEWS REIMAGINED: THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE PLATFORMISATION OF JOURNALISM

This exploratory study seeks to critically examine the role of social media in shaping local news production and distribution, following the ‘sociology of news’ (Schudson, 2012) tradition. The integration of applications generated by web 2.0, such as social media, in the news field, is characterized in the literature by a tension between the professional control of journalism and open participatory culture (Lewis, 2012). In this vein, we were able to observe two research trends: one that follows the changes that social media bring to journalism, restructuring it in the form of a network and increasing hybrid practices, and another that describes the tradition and continuity of journalism, social media being integrated into pre-existing institutional rules and routines (Papanagnou, 2020).

Furthermore, professional journalism is dealing with two processes: ‘platformisation’ (Poell et al., 2017) and ‘infomediation’ (Smyrnaioi & Rebillard, 2019). The first process involves a transition from the editorial model of news production and distribution to one in which the “content is continuously modulated, and re-packaged, informed by datafied user feedback” (Poell et al., 2017: 10). The second process relates to how social media platforms act as intermediaries between a vast, diverse yet standardized information supply and tailored user demand, employing algorithms and social data to curate editorially significant information collections, driven by a business model reliant primarily on user data gathering for marketing and advertising purposes (Smyrnaioi & Rebillard, 2019: 37).

In this context, social media platforms are understood as tools with potential for emancipation or commodification (Allmer, 2015) and as producers of two primary commodities: the audiences and the algorithms, both enhancing their influence and dominance in online behaviour (Bilić, 2018). Therefore, traditional concerns like ownership and production control regarding the media outlets must now be weighed against modern challenges like the worldwide dominance of search engines and social networking services (Bilić, Balabanić, 2017), that posits as intermediaries between media organizations and audiences.

Moreover, the editorial logic and the algorithmic logic “struggle with, and claim to resolve, the fundamental problem of human knowledge: how to identify relevant information crucial to the public” (Gillespie, 2014: 192).

The main research question of the study is: ‘To what extent do the perceived tensions of social media platform algorithms influence newsroom priorities and journalistic decision-making/ distribution?’ We hypothesize that approaches to social media in news production differ based on job roles: editor, chief-editor, or manager, and the specific stakes involved. Moreover, we anticipate discerning varied perceptions about the overarching influence of social media on the field of journalism, contingent upon one’s position in the media outlet.

The data collection tool will be an online questionnaire, with closed and open questions, applied to at least 5 local media institutions in Constanta that have a website where they constantly publish journalistic materials. We intend to target the editors, chief-editors, and managers and to use the convenience sampling method. The selected media institutions where the questionnaire will be sent will be heterogeneous from the perspective of ownership (public/private), the number of employees, the journalistic activity undertaken by approaching established journalistic genres (news, opinion materials, interviews, reports, investigations) and the predominant content format they produce (text, audio, video).

Keywords: platformisation; infomediation; local journalism; news production; sociology of news.

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Natalia VASILENDIUC

University of Bucharest, Romania, in cooperation with the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences at the State University of Moldova, the Independent Journalism Center in Moldova, the Association of Independent Press of Moldova, and various private and public media, ORCID: 0000-0001-9588-3069

MAPPING RISKS AND UNCERTAINTIES IN THE MOLDOVAN JOURNALISM LANDSCAPE: INSIGHTS FROM THE WORLD JOURNALISM STUDY 2021-2023

The World Journalism Studies 3 (WJS3) project undertakes a comprehensive global investigation of the risks and uncertainties faced by journalists, making a

crucial contribution to our understanding of journalism's adaptive strategies in different socio-political, economic, and cultural milieus. Based on a solid theoretical framework, WJS3 systematically assesses perceptions in key journalistic dimensions such as editorial autonomy, influences on journalism, journalistic roles, epistemologies, ethics, security, resilience and working conditions.

This summary demonstrates the culmination of the WJS3 project through a quantitative study of the Moldovan media landscape, focusing on the intricacies of risk and uncertainty. The study involved 343 participants representing a cross-section of media, including national dailies, weeklies, news outlets, TV and radio channels, online media and emerging start-ups, painting a nuanced picture of the Moldovan journalism community.

The study sheds light on the extent and causes of the risk to which Moldovan journalists and news organizations are exposed. The findings highlight the nuanced nature of risk, which includes facets such as editorial autonomy, influences on journalism, journalistic roles, epistemologies, professional ethics, security, and resilience, and working conditions. A comparative analysis with previous surveys (WJS2) shows dynamic changes in journalists' perceptions over time.

A notable finding is the identification of determinants that drive cross-national differences in how journalists conceptualize and manage risk and uncertainty. The study highlights the evolving dimensions of the Moldovan media landscape and offers insights into journalists' professional orientations and the contextual structures that influence their work. The findings reveal different coping mechanisms and adaptive strategies journalists use to respond to socio-political and cultural demands.

Methodologically, the research team followed a geographically distributed approach, with team members stationed in key Moldovan cities such as Chişinău, Bălţi, Ungheni, Cahul, Soroca and Orhei. This method ensures a nuanced understanding of Moldovan media dynamics, with local contributors providing invaluable insights and overviews.

At the end of the project, the collected data set forms a solid infrastructure for sustained research on journalism and risk in Moldova. The results provide an up-to-date snapshot of the state of journalism in a dynamically evolving global context and provide actionable insights for practitioners, policy makers and academics. This discourse fosters an informed dialogue about the complex challenges and opportunities shaping Moldova's media landscape in the context of the Worlds of Journalism Study.

Claudia WEGENER

Yulia YURTAEVA-MARTENS

Alissa DORNIER

Philipp EICHEL

Louisa Camille JUNG

Lara VERSCHRAGEN

Film University Babelsberg Konrad Wolf, Germany

BETWEEN PRIVATE AND PROFESSIONAL ROLES: HOW DO YOUNG JOURNALISTS PRESENT THEMSELVES ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS?

Between professionalism, authenticity, and the credible delivery of journalistic content, young journalists today, face various challenges, especially in the context of social media. The competition for attention in the job market reinforces the urgency of strengthening one's digital self through self-promotion by revealing or by sharing personal stories. In the process, the boundary between professional and personal content continue to blur.

Our study aimed to explore the professional self-concept and self-presentation of young German journalists in connection with the professional use of social media, as well as the separation of personal and professional content representation. The study followed a qualitative approach and employed eight semi-structured interviews. The collected data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis. The theoretical foundation for interpreting the results was based on the sociological approach of Erving Goffman from his work *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1959).

As a result, it became evident that the respondents are highly conscious of the staging of their own roles. The representation of their professional role on the digital stage can be used to profile their own image and advance their careers through self-promotion. References to personal aspects are a means to generate attention and underscore credibility. It is clear that a general presence on platforms like X or Instagram and the associated professional self-representation are already imparted to aspiring journalists during their education. It is a different story when it comes to the private use of social media and the question of how to reconcile it with the professional role.

References:

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Local Organizing Committee

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies:

Associate Professor **Romina Surugiu**

Lecturer **Nicoleta Elena Apostol**

Oscar Stănciulescu

Dana Mendolicchio

The ESA RN18 organising committee is led by:

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Digital Transformation, Media and Social Inequalities

Bucharest, Romania, 25-26 January 2024

Recent technological developments and transformations in media and communication require a global reflection on their effects and outcomes on society, democracy and business. The platformisation process with its institutional dimensions: data infrastructures, markets and governance (Poell, Nieborg & van Dijck, 2019) led to new business models and relationships between social, market and political actors. Journalism as an institution has been under question for over a decade or even two (Deuze, 2020) as the news industry is declining. Journalism as a profession strives to retain or regain the people's trust. With its recent advances artificial intelligence is seen as a threat or a chance for humanity. The AI's impact on the media and communication sector is open for debate. Is it a threat or an asset for professional practice?

At the same time, the hybridisation of communication professions – roughly defined as a mixture of journalistic and public relations and advertising&marketing practices in the digital context – adds new challenges in maintaining a fair and democratic public sphere and ensuring equal access to quality information.

Our focus is to foster an open academic debate on broad themes related to the outcomes of digital transformation in contemporary media and communication. We encourage contributions that adhere to the critical sociology perspective.

